

PERIYAR UNIVERSITY
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY (Ph.D.)
REVISED REGULATIONS
(As per UGC 2009 regulations)

1. PREAMBLE

The degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) is awarded to a candidate who, as per these regulations, has submitted a thesis on the basis of original and independent research in any particular discipline or involving more than one discipline (interdisciplinary), that makes a contribution to the advancement of knowledge, which is approved by suitably appointed examiners as required.

The Ph.D programme through distance education mode is not permissible.

The revised regulations should be followed in all aspects.

The registration will be automatically cancelled if any of the conditions/regulations/rules framed in this regulation is not adhered.

2. ELIGIBILITY

For the purpose of admission to Ph.D programme, a candidate should have obtained a Master Degree with not less than 55% of marks or an equivalent grade.

For the candidates belonging to SC/ST community and those who have qualified for the Master's degree before 19th September 1991 the minimum eligibility marks shall be 50% in their Master's degree.

Candidates can register under the following categories for the Ph.D. programme:

- a) Full Time (with or without stipend or fellowship)
- b) Part Time (teacher or non-teacher; internal vis-à-vis external)
- c) Research Fellows/Research Assistants/Technical Assistants/Project Assistants/Training Officers in Extension Departments approved by the University, appointed in the Research Projects funded by recognized Agencies /Government are also eligible to register for Ph.D. on a full time basis in the same department provided they satisfy the eligibility criteria laid down.

d) Independent Research without Supervisor:

The candidates belonging to any of the above categories may register in the University Departments, affiliated Colleges and Research Institutions coming under these regulations.

3. REGISTRATION FOR Ph.D. PROGRAMME

3.1. FULL TIME

The following candidates are eligible to register for the Full Time Ph.D. Programme:

A candidate who has qualified the Master Degree in the faculties of Arts, Sciences, Fine Arts, Languages, Commerce, Education and Management Science of this University or equivalent thereto.

3.2. PART TIME (INTERNAL)

A candidate, possessing any one of the qualifications prescribed above and falling under any of the following categories, is eligible to do research on a Part Time basis (i.e., can carry out research while continuing as teacher etc.)

- [a] A Teacher working in the Department of the University or in an affiliated College of the University with two years of experience.
- [b] A teacher working in Higher Secondary School or High School or Polytechnic with three years of experience within the territorial jurisdiction of the University.
- [c] A candidate employed other than as a teacher in a permanent job, within the territorial jurisdiction of the University with a minimum of four years working experience put in continuously after the qualifying degree and satisfying the rules framed separately by the Syndicate from time to time.
- [d] Research Assistants/Technical Assistants appointed by the University with two years of experience are eligible to register for Ph.D. degree on Part time basis in the same department.

Registration of candidates under clause a, b, c and d mentioned above automatically ceases when he /she leaves the employment.

3.3. PART TIME (EXTERNAL)

Notwithstanding anything contained in these regulations, candidates possessing any one of the qualifications from Periyar University prescribed under section of the Regulation, and employed as a teacher, scientist or in any other related capacity in National/State level Institutions and Universities, outside the territorial jurisdiction of this University, and who are sponsored by the respective organizations for pursuing research leading to the Ph.D. degree of this University on a Part Time basis, while continuing the employment may be permitted to register as external candidates. These candidates are permitted to do research in their place of employment and in addition they should undergo such course work prescribed by the **Doctoral Committee for a minimum period of six months directly under the Supervisor.**

3.4. INDEPENDENT RESEARCH WITHOUT SUPERVISOR

Teachers working in the Departments of Periyar University or in Colleges affiliated to Periyar University can register for Independent Research leading to Ph.D. degree without a Supervisor, provided they have completed four years of continuous teaching service.

A Doctoral Committee is to be formed as applicable to other candidates as per the relevant provisions of these regulations. This Doctoral Committee will monitor the research work of those registered under the clause and the Convenor of the Doctoral Committee will discharge the duties and responsibilities of the Supervisor.

4. DURATION OF RESEARCH

4.1. FULL TIME

A candidate registered as Full Time candidate for the Ph.D. degree possessing any one of the above qualifications shall work continuously in the department under the Supervisor concerned for a minimum period of THREE YEARS and maximum period of FIVE YEARS from the date of provisional registration but before the submission of thesis. However, a candidate may be allowed to seek an extension of SIX MONTHS subject to the recommendation of Doctoral Committee and approved by the University. Such extension may be availed for two times only.

4.2. PART TIME

A candidate registered for Ph.D. Degree as a Part Time candidate [both internal and external] shall work for a minimum period of FOUR YEARS and maximum period of SIX YEARS from the date of provisional registration before the submission of thesis. However, a candidate may be allowed to seek an extension of SIX MONTHS subject to the recommendation of Doctoral Committee and approved by the University. Such extension may be availed for two times only.

4.3. EXEMPTION

Exemption of one year both for Full Time and Part Time from the minimum duration required is permissible in respect of candidates who possess a M.Phil. or M.Litt., M.E., M.Tech., M.L., M.D., M.S., M. Pharm., M.V.Sc., in the relevant subject at the time of registration.

4.4. CONVERSION OF FULL TIME REGISTRATION INTO PART TIME AND VICE VERSA

Notwithstanding anything prescribed in these Regulations the University may permit conversion from Full Time research to Part Time research and vice versa in respect of candidates registered, for valid reasons and subject to satisfying the Regulations, Rules and Conditions in force. The period taken by the candidate will be worked out in the ratio of 2:3 for research work done before and after such a conversion.

4.5. RESIDENTIAL REQUIREMENTS

- [a] A candidate registered on a Full Time basis shall work for a minimum period of research prescribed above from the date of provisional registration and before submission of thesis in the Department or Institution under continuous supervision.
- [b] A candidate registered on Part Time (Internal) basis in all subjects except that involving laboratory work shall work at least for two months in every academic year during the course of research at the Institution where the Supervisor is serving. The Supervisor has to issue the attendance certificate which is to be forwarded by the Head of the Department to the Controller of Examinations.

- [c] Provided that those who have been permitted to be registered on a Part Time basis in subjects involving laboratory work in an institution other than where they are working, shall be required to work for a minimum total period of **six months** in the Institution directly under the Supervisor. If required, the period of **six months** of residency may be spent in **six spells** of not less than **thirty days** each during an academic year in the course of their research.
- [d] A candidate registered for the Ph.D. programme as a Part Time (**external**) candidate is expected to do research in his/her place of employment and in addition he/she should undergo such course work, examination and research work as may be prescribed by the University/Supervisor/Doctoral Committee for a minimum period of **SIX MONTHS** during the research period directly under the Supervisor in this University.

Provided, in all the above cases (a), (b), (c) and (d), the research work shall be monitored by the Doctoral Committee hereinafter prescribed, through periodical reports once in six months in the case of Full Time students and once in a year in the case of Part Time students in the prescribed proforma (Appendix – C).

5. SUBMISSION OF APPLICATION

5.1. APPLICATION FOR PROVISIONAL REGISTRATION

A candidate applying for provisional registration shall furnish all the information in the form prescribed together with the prescribed fee.

Every applicant who satisfies all the conditions and procedures prescribed shall, after approval by the University, be provisionally registered for the Degree.

5.2. INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

For Interdisciplinary research the proposal under interdisciplinary research should be submitted in the prescribed format (Appendix-A) duly approved by the Departmental Committee consisting of the members of the concerned departments along with the minutes forwarded by the Supervisor and the Head of the Department concerned to the University.

6. INSTITUTIONS WHERE RESEARCH CAN BE DONE

A candidate may be permitted to pursue research leading to the award of Ph.D. in any of the following institutions subject to the fulfillment of conditions of eligibility, availability of Supervisor and necessary facilities which are as follows:

- [a] The Departments of study and research of the University.
- [b] Departments of the colleges affiliated to the University and recognized by the University as having necessary facilities for carrying out research leading to the award of Ph.D. degree in the branch of study concerned provided that the department in the affiliated college should have been offering the post graduate/undergraduate courses in the concerned subjects for a minimum period of THREE years.
- [c] Research institutions duly recognized by the University.
- [d] Well equipped Research and Development Centers/Laboratories of public and private sector undertakings located in the territorial jurisdiction of the University recognized by the University as having necessary facilities for carrying out research at an advanced level.
- [e] The Syndicate may permit candidates who are working as teachers or in other related capacity in a Department of an affiliated college recognized for Research leading to the award of Ph.D. degree to register for the Ph.D. programme under a Supervisor in another institution within the territorial jurisdiction of the University area approved by the University for the purpose.
- [f] The Teacher candidates can register for Ph.D. programme with qualified Supervisors in any affiliated college in non-laboratory courses like Humanities, Languages, Social Sciences, Commerce, Mathematics and Statistics.

7. SUPERVISOR FOR RESEARCH

Every candidate registered for the Ph.D. programme shall work under the continuous supervision of a recognized Supervisor. For interdisciplinary research a candidate may have a Co-Guide. A Supervisor should not guide his /her immediate or close relative and to this effect he/she shall furnish a declaration in the column provided in the application form for admission.

7.1. QUALIFICATIONS AND RECOGNITION

7.1.1. A person who is in permanent employment may be recognized as a Supervisor for guiding researchers leading to the award of the Ph.D. degree in any faculty provided he/she possesses the following:

- [a] A Ph.D. degree of this University or of any other University recognized by the Syndicate as equivalent thereto
- [b] A minimum of total two years of UG/PG teaching experience in the concerned subject including one year of teaching or research experience after acquiring Ph.D. degree.
- [c] After the award of the Ph.D. degree he/she should have published atleast two papers in standard referred journal or equivalent published work as books or articles in edited books by reputed publishers.

7.1.2. Emeritus Scientists/Fellows/Professors of the University Departments or affiliated institutions recognized for research by the University who are funded by UGC/CSIR/ICAR and other Governmental/Non-Governmental funding agencies may also be permitted to guide Ph.D. students as per the guidelines listed below:

- [a] They may be allowed to guide Ph.D. scholars till they complete the age of 65 years. However, they shall not be allowed to register candidates beyond 60 years.
- [b] The maximum permissible number of candidates to be registered for the Ph.D. Programme is only six.

7.1.3. Emeritus/Honorary Professors in the University Departments may be permitted to guide Ph.D. scholars provided:

- [a] The request is made to the University with the consent of the Head of the Department where he/she would register the candidates for the Ph.D. programme.
- [b] They are allowed to guide Ph.D. students till they complete the age of 65 years. However, they shall not be allowed to register candidates after the completion of 60 years.
- [c] The maximum permissible number of candidates to be registered for the Ph.D. programme is only six.

7.1.4. Librarians, Deputy Librarians, Directors of Physical Education and Assistant Directors of Physical Education who are working in the University or in the affiliated Colleges or in recognized Research Institutions of the University may be permitted to guide a maximum of EIGHT candidates (Part Time) only at any given time in their respective field of specialization.

7.1.5. The research articles/book submitted for Ph.D.guideship shall be referred to any referee for approval.

7.1.6. The entire process of guideship shall be referred to Board of Research Studies for scrutiny.

7. 2. NUMBER OF CANDIDATES UNDER A SUPERVISOR

The total number of candidates registered for the Ph.D. programme, including Part Time scholars, at any point of time shall not exceed eight in the case of a Supervisor working in the Departments of the University/affiliated colleges or Research Institutions.

Faculty members having major research projects of **two years** duration (or) **more** with **Project fellow** can take two candidates for Ph.D. programme besides the stipulated strength of eight candidates.

Faculty members can also admit the candidates with national award/fellowships under this category. However, the total no. of candidates should not exceed ten.

8 candidates (teaching category only) are permitted to register for Ph.D under full-time / part-time category.

In case of non-teaching category maximum of 4 part-time candidates is permitted to register Ph.D, out of 8 candidates.

Vacancy in Ph.D. course will arise under a guide as and when the candidates already registered, submitted their thesis.

8. ADMISSION PROCEDURE

8.1. SESSIONS FOR ADMISSION

Application can be issued and submitted throughout the year for both Full Time and Part Time. Registration can be had on thrice in a year as follows.

Session		Last Date
Session - I	July	31st July
Session - II	November	30th November
Session - III	March	31st March

8.2. SELECTION PROCEDURE

The admission procedures could be completed by the Departmental Selection Committee of the University Departments/College Admission Committee/Research Institution Admission Committee, on the same lines of the M.A./M.Sc./P.G., admission procedures of the University Departments by following the State reservation policy, provided the following guidelines are adopted:

- [a] The admission to the Ph.D programme is based on the entrance test conducted at the University/Research Institute/College level.
- [b] The Minutes of the selection process duly signed by the departmental/research institution/college Admission Committee to be appended.
- [c] A checklist of Certificates to be verified and certified by the Admission Committee.
- [d] A brief research proposal (500 words) should be submitted along with the application.
- [e] With regard to a candidate proposing to work on the contribution of living author(s) necessary permission may be obtained from the concerned author(s).
- [f] Ph.D. permission Application forms along with the minutes should be forwarded to the University for approval.
- [g] The candidate with UGC/CSIR/SLET/NET/GATE/Teacher Fellowship/Project fellows/M.Phil are exempted from entrance test. However, they should appear for the interview organized by the School/Department/Institution/University/Colleges.

The admission should be made purely on merit basis.

- a) The Entrance Test, which will be conducted by the respective Department/College/Institution, shall carry a maximum of 50 marks as detailed below:

i. Written	-	40 marks
ii. Interview	-	10 marks
Total	-	50 marks

- b) The candidate should secure at least 25 marks out of 50 marks earmarked for the Entrance Test (Written and Oral).
- c) The remaining 50 marks shall be by converting the qualifying examination marks.
- d) The candidate should take the examination only in the subject for which he/she has applied for admission to the Ph.D. programme.
- e) The admission committee of the respective Departments/ colleges shall set the question paper for the entrance test and value the answer paper.
- f) The candidate with fellowship from UGC-NET, CSIR or SLET, candidate who has completed M.Phil. Course, Project Fellows appointed in the major research projects and teachers working in affiliated and constituent Colleges shall be exempted from appearing for the Entrance Test.
- g) If the candidates have passed Master's Degree in Grading system they may be asked to get equivalent marks or classification for the same from the University concerned and the same may be forwarded to the office with the selected list.
- h) The conditions for admission prescribed under the regulations in respect of the Ph.D. programme should be strictly followed. All candidates should have passed two year P.G degree course after three years degree course and higher secondary of 12 years duration or Pre-University under 11 year SSLC+1 year or 10+2 pattern. Candidates who have passed the P.G degree examination with less than 17 years of total duration of earlier courses as prescribed are not eligible for admission to Ph.D. programmes.
- i) Candidates who have passed their qualifying examination from other Boards/Universities must produce their migration certificate at the time of admission.
- j) While forwarding the selection list the following should be furnished.
 - (i) The applications of the candidates who have applied for the Ph.D. programme along with the enclosures.
 - (ii) List of the candidates applied, interviewed and selected.
 - (iii) Minutes of the Meeting of the Departmental Selection Committee with Signature of the Members.
 - (iv) A Checklist of certificates verified and certified by the Departmental Selection Committee.

- k) In the case of foreign candidates a Research visa obtained from the respective High Commission/Embassy or through Human Resource Development Ministry, Government of India, New Delhi, for the period of the Ph.D. programme be forwarded to the University.

The fees payable to the University should be collected from each candidate and remitted to the University after receipt of the communication regarding approval for admission to the Ph.D. programme from this University.

The fees payable by every research student admitted to the Departments are as prescribed by the Syndicate from time to time.

If it is observed at a later stage that the selection list given by the University Department/College/Research Institution is not in accordance with the rules, the University will cancel the same at any stage of the Ph.D. programme. The Heads of the Departments of the University/Principals/Directors should certify that the selections are made strictly on the basis of guidelines issued by the University.

8.3. ALLOCATION OF SUPERVISOR

The allocation of Supervisor for a selected student shall be decided by the Department in formal manner depending on the number of students per faculty member, the available specialization among the faculty Supervisors, and the research interest of the student as indicated during interview by the student. The allotment/allocation of Supervisor shall not be left to the individual student or teacher.

8.4. CHANGE OF SUPERVISOR

- a) Transfer of Ph.D. scholars from one Supervisor to another Supervisor can be possible, if mutual willingness is given by both the original and the new Supervisor provided the scholar has submitted periodical report as per norms.
- b) In case, change of Supervisor or transfer of candidates is proposed without the consent of any one of the parties concerned, the matter shall be referred to the Board of Research Studies, whose decision shall be final.
- c) The Supervisors who wish to avail leave/lien/deputation beyond a period of six months shall nominate Co-Guides in the concerned subject for the candidates registered with them and the fact is to be intimated to the University in advance.

- d) On expiry/demise of the supervisor, the candidate can be permitted to transfer his/her registration to another recognized supervisor.

9. CANCELLATION OF Ph.D. REGISTRATION

- a) In case of candidates who do not possess an M.Phil. degree/ have not taken Part I course work and examination and the minutes of the meeting of the Doctoral Committee for them are not forwarded to the University for confirmation of provisional registration on completion of one year of provisional registration, their registration shall be cancelled by the University by the 18th month from the date of provisional registration.
- b) In the case of recommendation for cancellation of the registration by the Supervisor, the candidate shall be intimated about the grounds on which the registration is being proposed for cancellation. In case of any representation from the candidate within two weeks, the Controller of Examinations shall refer the matter to the Board of Research Studies, which may either suggest cancellation or change of Supervisor based on the merit of the case. The decision of the Board of Research Studies shall be final.
- c) If the conditions are not fulfilled the registration will automatically be cancelled.

10. DOCTORAL COMMITTEE

For every candidate Full Time, Part Time, [Internal and External] and Independent candidates for the Ph.D. programme, a Doctoral Committee of not less than three members who are recognized Supervisors shall be constituted with the approval of the University as follows:

In respect of candidates registered for the Ph.D. degree under a Supervisor, either as Full Time or Part Time (Internal and External), the Doctoral Committee shall consist of the Supervisor as its Convener, the Head of the Department concerned, provided he/she is a recognized supervisor or his/her nominee, and one other member from other institutions, who is an expert in the subject.

In respect of interdisciplinary research, the Co-Guide shall also be included as a member, in addition to those members mentioned above.

The Doctoral Committee will have the functions as may be prescribed (Appendix-B). The scholars shall submit progress reports in the prescribed form (Appendix-C) once in six months in the case of Full Time candidates and once in a year in the case of Part Time candidates. The proceedings of the Doctoral Committee should be forwarded to the Controller of Examinations through the Head of the Department and the Supervisor should maintain a copy of the same in the department concerned.

11. EXAMINATION AND EVALUATION

11.1. COURSE WORK AND EVALUATION

Every candidate provisionally registered for the Ph.D. degree, shall, after undergoing the courses prescribed by the Doctoral Committee, has to appear for course work and oral examinations at the end of the first year after provisional registration.

Course work comprises of two courses viz.,

Course I

Research Methodology (M.Phil. candidates are exempted)

Course II

A Course in the specialized area of research framed by the concerned Supervisor and approved by the Doctoral Committee.

A candidate who is approved by the Doctoral Committee, on the basis of these examinations will be registered as a candidate for the Ph.D. degree thereafter confirming his/her provisional registration. He/she shall be permitted to proceed with his/her research work and submit the thesis, at the expiry of the minimum total period of research prescribed from the date of provisional registration. The candidate should give one seminar after registration in the area connected with his /her research and a second seminar on the topic of his/her research work.

If the candidate is not successful before Doctoral Committee in the first attempt, the candidate can appear again after six months provided he/she has passed the written examinations.

A candidate who is not found fit even after the second appearance and re-examination at the end of six months he/she shall not be permitted to continue research and his/her provisional registration shall be cancelled.

The Mark statement for the course work should be given to the candidate by the office of the Controller of Examination.

Upon satisfactory completion of course work and research methodology, which shall form part & parcel of Ph.D Programme, the Ph.D Scholar shall undertake research work and produce a

draft thesis within a reasonable time, as stipulated by the Institution concerned.

After the submission of synopsis and one month prior to submission of the thesis, the student shall make a pre Ph.D presentation in the Department that may be open to all faculty members and research students, for getting feedback and comments, which may be suitably incorporated into the thesis under the advice of the supervisor.

The Minutes of the presentation (pre viva) should be enclosed along with the thesis.

Ph.D candidates shall publish one research paper in a referred Journal before the submission of the thesis/monograph for adjudication, and produce evidence for the same in the form of acceptance letter or the reprint.

11.2. SUBMISSION OF SYNOPSIS

It is permitted to submit the synopsis 3 months before the minimum eligible period for Ph.D.

Not less than three months before the submission of the thesis, every candidate shall submit to the University, through the Supervisor or the Convener of the Doctoral Committee wherever relevant, a Synopsis (6 copies) of the proposed thesis together with the certificate of the Doctoral Committee after presenting the Synopsis, along with the prescribed application form and fee. The candidate shall state the title of the thesis and inform the probable date of submission of his/her thesis in the application. The Synopsis shall not exceed 20 typewritten or printed pages (one side only of A4 size).

Not later than six months after the submission of the Synopsis and after the expiry of the minimum period of research prescribed, every candidate shall submit **FIVE** copies of the thesis embodying the results of the research carried out by him/her, along with a C.D. and the prescribed application form and fee.

No candidate shall ordinarily be permitted to submit his/her thesis after a period of five years in the case of Full Time research and six years in the case of Part Time research; provided that the University may for valid reasons and on the recommendations of his/her Supervisor, grant extension of time for not more than two years in all, to the candidate. A candidate, who is not able to submit his/her thesis even after the grant of extension of two years, shall have his/her registration cancelled.

The Ph.D. thesis/Synopsis shall be written in English for subjects other than languages. A one page abstract about the thesis should be given in Tamil. However, if the candidate prefers to submit the synopsis/Thesis in Tamil it shall be permitted.

11.3. SUBMISSION OF THESIS

The title page of the thesis, cover, format, etc., should strictly be in conformity with the format of presentation as prescribed (Appendix–D) and the thesis (all copies) should carry a declaration (Appendix–E) by the candidate and certificate (Appendix–F) duly signed and issued by the Supervisor. The thesis should not be hard bound and it should have a thin and flexible cover.

The soft copy of the thesis in the CD form should also be submitted along with thesis for forwarding the same to the UGC.

11.3.1. SUBMISSION OF THESIS BEFORE THE MINIMUM PERIOD PRESCRIBED

Notwithstanding anything contained in these regulations regarding the minimum period of research to be put in by candidates before becoming eligible to submit their thesis for the degree, it shall be competent for the Syndicate, to permit candidates to submit their thesis earlier by a period of not exceeding six months provided such request for earlier submission from the candidates is accompanied by:

- [a] The recommendation of the Supervisor for relaxation based on the satisfactory completion of research work for the thesis with evidence that the candidate has been working consistently even prior to his/her provisional registration for the Ph.D., degree, on the topic of his/her research.
- [b] Evidence of having completed the required work for the thesis by way of at least one publication in the topic of Ph.D. research in referred journal.

11.4. RE-REGISTRATION

A candidate, who has not submitted the thesis but completed course work at the end of seven/eight years may choose to re-register with the prescribed fees. In such instances, the re-registered candidate shall be permitted to submit his/her thesis after a period of one year but not later than two years, only if the Supervisor recommends and the topic of the thesis remains unchanged.

For re-registered candidates with change of Supervisor and/or topic of thesis, the required period would be similar to other candidates seeking registration for the first time.

11.5. ADJUDICATION OF Ph.D. THESIS

11.5.1. EXAMINERS

The Vice-Chancellor may appoint a Board of Examiners for valuation of thesis consisting as follows:

- a) One from outside the country (panel with 3 names/experts).
- b) One from outside Tamilnadu (panel with 3 names/experts).
- c) Supervisor as internal examiner.
- d) For viva-voce panel with in Tamilnadu ie. outside Periyar University jurisdiction (panel with 3 names/experts).

None of the names so suggested be an immediate relative of the candidate.

Provided that the persons suggested for appointment as Examiners should have a Ph.D. degree with teaching and/or research experience for at least 10 years at the post graduate level with research publications.

In subjects like Indian languages the panel of Examiners may be from within India subject to specific justification by the Supervisor.

The Board of Examiners so appointed shall evaluate the thesis and submit a report on the merit of the candidate for the award of the Ph.D. degree. Each Examiner is expected to give a detailed report on the thesis apart from a proforma for adjudication in the format prescribed (Appendix-G).

The Board of Examiners shall report on the merit of the candidate as “Highly Commended”, “Commended” or “Not Commended”.

The two External Examiners shall send the individual reports together with the proforma to the Convener and a copy to the Controller of Examinations who will forward the same to the University together with his/her individual report, the proforma and also a consolidated report of the Board bringing out the salient points made in the individual reports.

If all the three Examiners unanimously recommend the award of the degree, the candidate will be asked to appear for a public Viva Voce examination.

The candidate should carry out the corrections etc, if any, suggested by the Examiners, before the public Viva Voce examination. The Supervisor shall furnish a certificate to this effect, together with the list of corrections, to the University before the said examination.

If one of the External Examiners recommends the award of the degree and the other does not recommend the award, the Vice-Chancellor may refer the thesis to a fourth Examiner for evaluation, provided that the fourth Examiner so appointed shall

belong to the same category (i.e from India or outside India) as the original Examiner who evaluated the thesis and has not recommended.

The fourth Examiner will not be provided with the report of the other examiners. If the fourth Examiner recommends the award of the degree, the candidate will be asked to appear for a public Viva Voce examination. If the fourth Examiner also does not recommend the award of the degree, the degree will not be awarded to the candidate.

The remarks made by the Examiner who has not recommended the award, will be provided to the Supervisor so as to enable him to advise the candidate to carry out the corrections/ additions/ alterations/modifications suggested by the examiners, subject to the needs as judged by the Supervisor before the public Viva Voce examination.

A candidate whose thesis has not been recommended for the award of the degree may be permitted to re-submit it on a second occasion within a period of one year from the date of declaration of the results within specific statement from the candidate and the Supervisor about the additional research work conducted and revision done in the thesis.

If any Examiner has made some comments and suggested corrections/modification/alterations while not recommending the thesis and asking the candidate to resubmit the thesis, the candidate will be informed accordingly through the Supervisor. The resubmitted thesis shall be referred to the same Examiner who originally evaluated the thesis for re-evaluation.

11.6. PUBLIC VIVA VOCE EXAMINATION

A candidate whose thesis has been recommended for the award of Ph.D. degree by the Board of Examiners for award of Ph.D. has to submit himself /herself to a public Viva Voce examination conducted by the Viva Voce Board/with Supervisors/Convener and one External Examiner appointed by the Vice-Chancellor. The Indian Examiner, who evaluated the thesis, shall as far as possible be appointed as External Examiner to conduct the public Viva Voce examination for the candidate. Members of the department in the subject concerned where the candidate conducted research and outside specialists, if any and those who are interested in the subject matter may participate in the public Viva Voce examination. The Supervisor shall convey to the University, the result of such public Viva Voce examination duly endorsed by the External Examiner, together with a list of participants in the examination with their signatures, designations

and addresses. A candidate who is also successful at the public Viva Voce examination shall be declared to have qualified for the award of Ph.D. degree.

A copy of the thesis of the candidate appearing for the public Viva Voce examination shall be kept in the departmental library for perusal of those interested in the thesis before the conduct of the public Viva Voce examination, together with appropriate public notice issued by the Supervisor for the purpose.

If for any valid reason, the Supervisor is unable to conduct the public Viva Voce examination, the Vice-Chancellor may appoint a suitable Examiner, in his/her place in such cases.

A candidate, who submits a satisfactory thesis but is not successful at the public Viva Voce examination, may be permitted to take the same on a second occasion, before the same board after the expiry of six months. If he/she is not successful even on the second occasion at the public Viva Voce examination, the degree will not be awarded to him/her.

No candidate shall be permitted to submit a thesis or to appear for the public Viva Voce examination on more than two occasions.

11.7. FORMAT OF DEGREE

Along with the Degree, the Degree and Provisional Certificate certifying to the effect that the Degree has been awarded in accordance with the provisions of the 2009 regulations of the UGC.

The Ph.D. degree certificate shall be as in Appendices I and J.

In the case of the award of the Ph.D. degree for interdisciplinary research, the degree certificate shall bear both the subjects of the candidate's post-graduate degree and the discipline of the department in which the candidate has conducted his doctoral research mentioning them as "interdisciplinary" (Appendices K).

12. PUBLICATION OF THESIS

A thesis, whether approved or not, shall not be published without the permission of the Syndicate and the Syndicate may grant permission for the publication under such conditions as it may impose.

Provided that a candidate may, during the course of his/her research, publish papers in standard research journals, as advised by his/her Supervisor, but the thesis as a whole shall not be published without obtaining permission of the Syndicate mentioned above.

Permission for publication of the thesis should be made within five years after the award of the degree.

12.1 SOFT COPY OF THE THESIS TO UGC

Following the successful completion of the evaluation process and announcements of the award of Ph.D, the University shall submit a soft copy of the Ph.D thesis to the UGC within a period of thirty days, for hosting the same in INFLIBNET, accessible to all Institutions/Universities.

13. Specifications of requirements for according Institution/ Department recognition to conduct research leading to Ph.D.:

1. Minimum two persons with Ph.D. qualifications in the area(s) of research by the Department/Institution as approved by the University.
2. Library facilities with adequate books, journals in the area of Research literature retrieval facility through CD-ROM/Internet facilities.
3. Laboratories with equipments as required for the discipline of research for which recognition sought (specific details to be provided by the respective Boards of Studies for the disciplines concerned)
4. Adequate working space for the research students in terms of laboratories, study rooms, seminar room facilities etc.
5. Faculty Research Profile of the Department seeking recognition along with the department/faculty contributions made in the respective fields.
6. Proportionate increase of hostel, canteen and student amenities.
7. Details of existing infrastructure facilities of the Department/Institution.

13.1. Regarding recognition of personnel working in R and D laboratories of private and public sector undertakings/ similar Institutions of Languages, Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences, Commerce, Management Sciences and Medical Sciences.

1. There should be a recognized Co-Guide for each student in the concerned University Department/Affiliated PG Colleges recognized as Centers for conducting research leading to Ph.D. Degree.

2. There should be at least three personnel to be recognized as Guides in the R and D centres/similar institutions of Languages, Humanities, Arts, Social Sciences, Sciences, Commerce, Management Sciences and Medical Sciences. This is necessary because in the event of the personnel/guide leaving the organization the students may be shifted to one of the remaining research personnel.
3. The organization should permit the students to publish/present the paper in the National/International Conferences.
4. Researchers with Ph.D. degree who fulfill the norms of the University may be recognized as Guides from the designation Senior Manager (R and D)/equivalent cadres.
5. The students should pay the fees prescribed to the University.
6. It is the responsibility of the R and D Centres/Institutions to provide the facilities and resources to the students until he/she completes his/her Ph.D. work.

PERIYAR UNIVERSITY
14. Admission to Ph.D. Programme

(i) List of Candidates applied

Sl.No.	Application No.	Name of the Candidate	Community OC/BC/MBC/SC/ST	Marks in PG Examination Average percentage.
1.				
2.				

(ii) List of Candidates interviewed

No.	Name of the Candidate	Community OC/BC/MBC/SC/ST	Marks in P.G. Exams 50	Marks in Entrance Examination.			Grand total P.G.Exams + E.E. 100
				Written 40	Oral 10	Total 50	
1.							
2.							

(iii). List of Candidates selected (in the above format)

(Signatures of the Members of the Departmental Committee)

APPENDIX – A

FORMAT FOR INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH PROPOSAL

(This format should be forwarded along with the Minutes of the
Departmental Committee)

PARTICULARS OF THE CANDIDATE

1. Name :
2. Age and date of birth :
3. Academic Qualification :
4. Occupation/ Designation :
5. Details of Organization if employed :

a) Name of organization with address	b) Nature of Work	c) Duration of employment
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6. The subject in which the candidate has qualified for Master's Degree :
7. The proposed other discipline in which the candidate intends to work for Ph.D. :
8. The proposed department where the candidate intends to work for Ph.D. with address :
9. The brief write-up of the proposed research (not more than 400 words (attach separate sheet)) :
10. Whether the proposed Ph.D. work is partly, directly or indirectly related to the branch of knowledge in which the candidate has qualified for his/her Master's degree :
11. Briefly describe in (not more than 50 words) the input from the two disciplines to the proposed area of research for Ph.D. (attach separate sheet) :
12. Do you have any publications bearing

interdisciplinary research, pertaining
to your chosen theme for Ph.D. research?
If yes, furnish the details.

:

13. Comments of the Supervisor under
whom you propose to do
interdisciplinary research

:

SIGNATURE OF THE SUPERVISOR
(name and seal)

SIGNATURE OF THE APPLICANT

SIGNATURE OF THE CO-GUIDE
(name and seal)

**SIGNATURE OF THE
HEAD OF THE DEPARTMENT**
(name and seal)

Place:

Date:

APPENDIX – B

FUNCTIONS OF THE DOCTORAL COMMITTEE

(1) To discuss advice and recommend on all matters connected with the candidate's research from provisional registration to the time of submission of thesis.

(2) To suggest courses to be undertaken by the candidate during the first year of his provisional registration and with a view to fulfill the requirements of the research.

Such courses of instruction may be given as short term courses lasting from three to four months in such subjects as may be chosen by the Doctoral Committee.

(3) To examine the candidate by written and oral examinations, on the completion of such courses, at the end of the first year of provisional registration and to report to the University on the fitness or otherwise of the candidate to proceed with his research work for the Ph.D. degree and recommending the confirmation of the provisional registration.

In case where a candidate is not approved at the end of the first year by the Doctoral Committee, it may recommend that the candidate should undergo additional course for a further period of not exceeding 6 months, at the end of which he shall be examined again; and if found fit, his provisional registration will be confirmed and he will be permitted to proceed with his research work;

A candidate who is not found fit even after the additional course and re-examination, shall not be permitted to continue the research and his provisional registration shall stand cancelled.

(4) To monitor the candidate's work periodically by directing him [a] to give periodical seminars on his work [b] to submit progress reports once in every six months to the University on the candidate's progress of his research work in the prescribed format [c] to conduct and supervise a presentation by the candidate of the final draft of his proposed thesis for approval before the submission of Synopsis of the thesis to the University and to give a certificate to this effect to be submitted along with the Synopsis.

(5) The Doctoral Committee shall meet atleast twice, first meeting at the end of the first year during provisional registration and the second before the submission of Synopsis.

APPENDIX – C
PROGRESS REPORT OF Ph.D. PROGRAMME

(1). The progress report shall be submitted in the prescribed format by the candidate in triplicate to the Supervisor accompanied by a report by the candidate about the work carried out during this period (in about 300 words) duly signed by the candidate and countersigned by the Supervisor.

(2). The Supervisor shall fill his part, sign it and get it countersigned by the Head of the Department concerned.

(3). One copy shall be sent to the Controller of Examinations through proper channel and the second copy shall be sent to the sponsoring institution wherever applicable.

(4). The report should be submitted on or before 10th January, 10th April, 10th July and 10th October of every year.

1. Particulars about the Candidate:

- [a] Name :
- [b] Designation :
- [c] Institution where employed
(if applicable) :
- [d] Period of the Report - January/
April/July/October :

2. Registration Details

- [a] Category of Registration : Full Time.....
: Part Time.....
: (Internal).....
: Part Time.....
: (External).....
- [b] Date of Provisional Registration
with University Reference Details :
- [c] Has the Provisional Registration
been confirmed ? : Yes.....
No.....
- If Yes, give reference :

3. Particulars of the Supervisor(s) :

- [i] Supervisor :
- a) Name :
- b) Designation :
- c) Institution(s) where employed :

- [ii] Supervisor :
- a) Name :
- b) Designation :
- c) Institution(s) where employed :
4. Name of the Department/Institution where research is conducted :
5. Area of work and tentative title of proposed thesis :
6. Details of progress :
- a) Details of report showing Research Progress :
- b) Details of Research Papers published :
- c) Details of Conference Papers published :
- d) Details of Seminars/ Conferences Attended :
- e) Details of prescribed course work Completion :
7. Details of fees prescribed paid :

Date:

Signature of the Candidate

8. Remarks of the Supervisor
- a) Attendance : Satisfactory/
Not Satisfactory
- b) Progress : Satisfactory/
Not Satisfactory
- c) Expected time of completion :
- d) Recommendation :

Place:

Signature of the Supervisor

Date:

(name and seal)

Signature of the Head of the Department
(name and seal)

Signature of the Head of the Institution
(name and seal)

APPENDIX – D

**MODEL FOR COVER AND TITLE PAGE OF Ph.D. THESIS
(University Department)**

**A Study on Job Satisfaction of
Bank Employees in Salem District**

Thesis submitted to Periyar University in partial
fulfilment of the requirements for the award of degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in

By

.....

(Name of the Candidate)

Under the Guidance of

.....

(Name of the Supervisor)

Department of

**Periyar University
Salem – 636 011**

Month and Year

APPENDIX – E

**MODEL FOR COVER AND TITLE PAGE OF Ph.D. THESIS
(Affiliated College)**

**A Study on Job Satisfaction of
Bank Employees in Salem District**

Thesis submitted to Periyar University in partial
fulfilment of the requirements for the award of degree of
Doctor of Philosophy in

By

.....

(Name of the Candidate)

Under the Guidance of

.....

(Name of the Supervisor)

Affiliated College Logo

Department of

College Name

Place – Pincode

(Affiliated to Periyar University)

Month and Year

**Name and Official
Address of Supervisor**

APPENDIX – F
CERTIFICATE

I certify that the thesis entitled
.....submitted to Periyar University in partial
fulfilment for the award of degree of Doctor of Philosophy in
.....is a bonafide research work
carried out by him/her under my guidance and supervision
and it has not formed the basis for the award of any Degree,
Diploma, Associateship, Fellowship or any other similar titles
in this or any other University or Institution of higher
learning.

Place:

Signature of the Supervisor.

Date:

APPENDIX – G
DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the thesis entitled
.....
submitted to Periyar University in partial fulfilment of the
requirements for the award of the degree of Doctor of
Philosophy in.....
is a record of original research work carried out by me under
the guidance and supervision of.....
and that it has not formed before the basis for the award of
any Degree, Diploma, Associateship, Fellowship or any other
similar titles in this or any other University or Institution of
higher learning.

Place:

Signature of Candidate.

Date

APPENDIX – H

PROFORMA FOR ADJUDICATION OF THE Ph.D. THESIS

- 1. Name of the Candidate :
- 2. Title of the thesis :
- 3. Discipline and Subject :
- 4. Name and Address of Examiner :
- 5. Recommendations of the Examiner
(Please strike out whichever is
not applicable) :

(a) Thesis is highly commended and degree may be awarded

or

(b) Thesis is commended and degree may be awarded

or

(c) Thesis is commended and degree may be awarded subject to the candidate furnishing satisfactory clarification to my queries during the public Viva Voce.

or

(d) Thesis is commended and degree may be awarded subject to the condition that the corrections/modification, suggested by me are carried out in the thesis and duly certified by the Supervisor-Convenor before the Viva Voce examination.

or

(e) Thesis is not commended and is recommended for resubmission to me incorporating modifications suggested by me

or

(f) Thesis is not commended and the degree may not be awarded.

NOTE:

Please enclose your detailed report on the thesis. Please also enclose a list of questions, if any, to be asked at the public Viva Voce examination.

6. Whether recommended for publication : Yes/No

7. Suggestions if any, for incorporation
at the time of publication :

Place:
Date: Signature of the Examiner
(name and seal)

APPENDIX – I

Sample of Degree Certificate issued by the University

PERIYAR UNIVERSITY

FACULTY OF ARTS

The Syndicate of Periyar University hereby makes known that (Name of the candidate) has been admitted to the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in,..... he/she having been certified by duly appointed examiners to be qualified to receive the same in the year for the thesis entitled (Thesis Title).

“Dreams and Realities in the Novels of Kamala Markandaya” (English)

Given under the seal of Periyar University thisday of

This certificate is issued in accordance with the provision of the UGC regulations-2009.

Place:

Date:

REGISTRAR

VICE-CHANCELLOR

APPENDIX – J

PERIYAR UNIVERSITY

FACULTY OF SCIENCE

The Syndicate of Periyar University hereby makes known that (Name of the candidate) has been admitted to the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in,..... he/she having been certified by duly appointed examiners to be qualified to receive the same in the year for the thesis entitled (Thesis Title).

“The Modulating Effect of Tocophorol on Doxorubicin induced Changes in Rats” (Biochemistry).

Given under the seal of Periyar University thisday of

This certificate is issued in accordance with the provision of the UGC regulations-2009.

Place:

Date:

REGISTRAR

VICE-CHANCELLOR

APPENDIX – K

PERIYAR UNIVERSITY

INTERDISCIPLINARY DEGREE CERTIFICATE

The Syndicate of Periyar University hereby makes known that (Name of the candidate) has been admitted to the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in,..... he/she having been certified by duly appointed examiners to be qualified to receive the same in the year for the thesis entitled (Thesis Title).

**“Biophysical Characterisation of Biological Tissues”
(Theoretical Physics - Zoology Interdisciplinary).**

Given under the seal of Periyar University thisday of

This certificate is issued in accordance with the provision of the UGC regulations-2009.

Place:

Date:

REGISTRAR

VICE-CHANCELLOR

* * * *

/22nd BORS-Regulations- Ph. D - 2013 /Feb 2013/1892